

VARIOUS METRICS: A FOCUS ON GOOGLE SCHOLAR - A CASE STUDY

Dr. Ravikumar N.S

Librarian, Government First Grade College in Yelahanka,
Bengaluru- 560064, Karnataka, India

Dr. Hemantha Kumar G.H

Veterinary College in Hebbal, Bengaluru – 560024, India

Abstract

This study compares Google Scholar with other research evaluation tools like Web of Science and Scopus, analyzing their strengths and weaknesses. It delves into various metrics used in academic research evaluation, such as citation counts, h-index, and journal-level metrics like Impact Factor. The study also explores modern metrics like altmetrics, i10 index, G-index, and h-core. Launched in 2004, Google Scholar offers comprehensive research coverage, including web citations and references, outperforming Web of Science and Scopus. Google Scholar Metrics and Scopus provide h-index and citation counts for research evaluation, along with metrics like Eigenfactor, CiteScore, and Altmetrics for impact assessment. Google Scholar Metrics assist authors in gauging the impact of their recent articles in scholarly publications. The top 100 publications are ranked based on their five-year h5-index and h5-median metrics, covering articles published between 2019 and 2023 with citations in Google Scholar up to July 2024. The top 10 publications are determined by their combined h5-index and h5-median scores, with the New England Journal of Medicine ranking first at 13.26% and Nature at 12.29%. The study also lists the top 10 funding agencies supporting the indexing of journals in the country on Google Scholar, with the European Commission leading at 87% and the Government of Spain at 80%. Google Scholar indexes 8 major subjects globally, with the highest number of publications in health and medical sciences (69 subcategories) and engineering and computer science (56). It includes non-English publications from Africa, Asia, and Central and South America, making it a valuable tool for searching scholarly literature across disciplines. Users can access scholarly literature, including articles, theses, and books, from academic publishers, professional societies, and online repositories. Key features include searching for literature, exploring related works, citations, authors, and publications, accessing complete documents, staying updated on research, and tracking citations through a public author profile. This study tested the hypothesis.

Keywords: *Google Scholar, Metrics, Impact Factor, Altmetrics, H-index & Citations.*

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1. Introduction

Understanding research metrics is crucial for monitoring your journal's performance. This guide will help you navigate metrics like Impact Factor and usage statistics to choose the most suitable ones for your journal. Metrics are used in academic publishing to measure research impact, such as citation counts by subject or author and article citation frequency. This article explores journal-level, article-level, and author-level metrics, each with its own impact. By familiarizing yourself with these metrics, you can better align your research goals. Research metrics are essential tools for measuring performance at journal and author levels. The Impact Factor is a traditional metric, but there are now various metrics like Altmetrics and the h-index. Understanding how each metric is calculated and which ones are relevant to your journal is crucial. By using these tools, you can effectively track your journal's performance. For a comprehensive understanding of research metrics, download our guide or continue reading for an in-depth analysis of different metrics and how to interpret them. Google Scholar Metrics provide authors with a convenient way to assess the visibility and impact of their recent articles in scholarly publications, helping them decide where to publish their new research.

Scholar Metrics focus on recent scholarly articles, excluding smaller publications. Metrics like citation metrics, h-index, and h-median help identify top publications. Create your author profile on Google Scholar Citations by logging in with your Google Account, adding citations, affiliation, and research interests. Your profile showcases publications, citations, and metrics. The "Cited by" section displays total citations, the h-index shows the highest number of publications with at least that many citations, and the i10-index represents publications with at least 10 citations. To add an unpublished paper, upload the PDF to a public website, add the link to your profile, ensure clear title and author display, and include a labeled bibliography. Google Scholar and Scopus offer h-index and citation counts for research impact assessment, but consider other factors too.

2. Brief details of various research metrics in the world

Research metrics are quantitative indicators used to evaluate the impact and quality of research outputs. Some common research metrics include:

2.1 Impact Factor

The Impact Factor is a widely recognized metric used to evaluate journal performance. Originally created in the 1960s to assist librarians in managing collections, it has since become a popular measure of journal quality.

The Impact Factor is a simple research metric that indicates the average number of citations received by articles in a journal over a two-year period. The official results are published annually in the Web of Science Journal Citation Reports (JCR).

To calculate the 2020 impact factor, divide the total number of citations received by articles published in 2018 and 2019 by the total number of citable items published in those years. For example, if the total citations for 2018 and 2019 articles in 2020 are 200 and the total citable items for 2018 and 2019 are 73, the 2020 Impact Factor would be calculated as $200/73 = 2.73$.

The impact factor is a metric that indicates how often articles in a journal are cited, on average. Journals with higher impact factors are cited more frequently and are typically considered more prestigious.

2.2 Eigenfactor

In 2007, the Web of Science JCR introduced Eigenfactors and Article Influence Scores as alternative metrics to the Impact Factor. Eigenfactors measure a journal's influence by analyzing its citations in reputable journals over a five-year period. The Eigenfactor algorithm ranks journals based on citations received, excluding self-citations and considering subject areas. Eigenfactors are scaled so that the sum of all journal Eigenfactors in the JCR equals 100. The Eigenfactor score, available at <http://www.eigenfactor.org>, is a metric similar to the impact factor but excludes self-citations within the same journal. It is calculated over a five-year period using data from the JCR and indicates a journal's influence within its field. A high Eigenfactor score signifies significant impact without self-citation bias. To assess a researcher's overall impact, consider both their h-index and the Eigenfactor score of the journals they publish in. For more details, refer to the JCR glossary.

2.3 Article Influence Score

The Article Influence Score measures the average influence of a journal's articles in the first five years after publication. A score above 1.00 indicates higher-than-average influence. The calculation is based on the journal's Eigenfactor and the number of articles published over five years, compared to all journals. Scores are normalized so that the average journal in the JCR has a score of 1. Journals must be covered by the JCR for at least five years to receive an Article Influence Score.

2.4 CiteScore

CiteScore is a metric that measures the citations received by research published in a journal. It is available for journals and book series indexed in Scopus. Unlike the Impact Factor, CiteScore considers all content published in a journal, not just articles and reviews. Introduced by Scopus in December 2016, CiteScore can be easily accessed through the Scopus database. Scopus also offers additional rankings, such as the CiteScore percentile by subject categories and a monthly CiteScore tracker. The calculation for CiteScore involves dividing the number of citations received by content published in a journal in the last three years by the total number of items published in the journal during the same period.

Journals with a significant amount of front matter, like editorials or peer commentaries, may have lower CiteScores compared to Impact Factors, as this content is less likely to be cited. Citation Count refers to the number of times a research paper has been cited by other researchers, with a higher count indicating greater impact and influence. Data sources for Total Citations Count include Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus.

2.5 SNIP (Source Normalized Impact per Paper)

SNIP is a journal-level metric that aims to facilitate comparisons between journals across different disciplines. It uses Scopus data to measure the citations a journal receives relative to what is expected in its subject field. SNIP is calculated by dividing the journal's citation count per paper by the citation potential in the field. This metric is normalized to enable comparisons across disciplines, taking into account factors like the length of reference lists in publications. SNIP only considers citations from specific content types like articles, reviews, and conference papers, excluding citations from sources classified as "non-citing sources" by Scopus, such as trade journals and some Arts & Humanities titles.

2.6 SJR (SCImago Journal Rank)

The SJR measures the impact of a journal based on its subject field, quality, and reputation. It evaluates the prestige of a journal by considering the sources that cite it, giving more weight to citations from journals with higher SJR values. The formula for calculating SJR is the average number of weighted citations to a journal in a year divided by the number of articles published in the journal over the previous three years. SJR, like SNIP and CiteScore, uses Scopus data to determine journal rankings.

2.7 Altmetrics

Altmetrics is the creation and study of new metrics based on the social web for analyzing and informing scholarship." - The Altmetrics Manifesto

Altmetrics, also known as alternative metrics, were introduced in 2010 by Jason Priem in the Altmetrics Manifesto. Altmetrics provide a different way to measure and evaluate scholarly outputs beyond traditional citation counts. These metrics can be applied to various types of research outputs, such as articles, books, datasets, code, and preprints. When you visit a journal's website, you may find links to view metrics for individual articles or see an Altmetric doughnut, a colorful circle with a number at its center. While not all journals offer these metrics, many articles now come with quantitative indicators showing how they have been viewed and shared.

Altmetric calculates a score based on the online attention an article receives. The colored threads in the circle represent different types of online attention, with the number in the center being the Altmetric score. Social media and mainstream news media are the primary sources contributing to the score, while reference managers like Mendeley are also tracked but do not affect the score. Older articles tend to score higher due to more time for exposure, so Altmetric includes context data for articles of similar age.

The list includes mainstream news articles and blogs that reference the article, but not all media links are detectable by Altmetric. The list is curated and updated hourly. For example, you can check the metrics for a 2016 publication in Nature at this link: <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature19332/metrics>. The metrics cover citation counts, mentions in news/blogs/Google+, online attention, and Twitter demographics. The page displays the number of tweets and blogs discussing the article, links from Facebook pages, mentions on Google+, and references to news articles and blogs. Altmetric also releases an annual list of the most talked-about journal articles from the previous year. Altmetrics are alternative metrics that capture online attention and engagement around a research output, including social media mentions, downloads, and views.

2.8 NAAS Score

The National Academy of Agricultural Sciences (NAAS) is an Indian organization established in 1990 to promote excellence in agricultural research and publications. The NAAS Score is a metric used to evaluate the quality and impact of journals in the field. Journals with Thomson Reuters' Impact Factor receive a score of 6.00 plus the journal's Impact Factor, with a cap of 20. The NAAS rating system evaluates journals based on criteria such as originality, peer review process, citation impact, and contribution to agricultural science advancement. Factors like frequency of publication, editorial board constitution, article contributions from overseas, and citation analysis are considered in the evaluation process.

The NAAS score is calculated based on a combination of the journal's impact factor and the NAAS's assessment. Journals are categorized into two groups:

Category 1: includes journals with an impact factor from Thompson Reuters. The NAAS score for these journals is determined as 6 plus the impact factor, with a maximum cap of 20.

Category 2: consists of journals evaluated by the NAAS board.

3. What are the different metrics used to measure journal, article and author level impact?

There are several metrics used to measure the impact of journals, articles, and authors. These metrics can be found in databases like Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, and publisher websites. Researchers can use these metrics to evaluate the impact of their work, identify influential journals, and track their research impact over time. Some common metrics include:

3.1 Journal-Level Metrics

Journal-level metrics, such as the journal impact factor, are crucial for evaluating a journal's influence in the scientific community.

1. The Impact Factor is a widely used metric that calculates the average number of citations received by articles, proceedings, or reviews published in a journal over the past two years. It is published in the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) and is updated annually. The 5-year Impact Factor provides a longer-term perspective on journal metrics. The Journal Impact Factor (JIF) measures the average number of citations received by articles published in a

journal over a specific time period, serving as a tool to assess the prestige and influence of a journal within its field.

2. Eigenfactor is a metric that evaluates the importance of a journal based on the number of citations it receives, giving more weight to citations from prestigious journals and excluding self-citations. It calculates the average number of citations in a year to papers published in the last 5 years. Eigenfactor is included in the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) and uses data from Web of Science.
3. SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) is a metric that assigns more importance to citations from prestigious journals. It calculates the average number of weighted citations received in a year by articles published in the last 3 years. SJR uses data from Scopus to generate country and journal-specific rankings. SJR is published in SCImago Journal and Country Rank reports.
4. Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP) is a metric based on the weighted citations in a year to papers published in the last three years. It is published in CWTS Journal Indicators and the data for this indicator is sourced from Scopus. SNIP corrects the differences in citation practices in different disciplines, making it easier to compare this metric across various fields.
5. CiteScore is a metric introduced by Scopus that includes indicators like Cite Score Tracker, Cite Score Percentile, and Citation Count. It is calculated based on the citations received by articles in a journal over a three-year period, similar to the Journal Impact Factor.
6. H5 Index: this metric measure the number of articles published in the last five years that have at least the same number of citations as the number of articles. It can be accessed through Google Scholar.
7. Immediacy Index is the average number of article citations in the year of publication, indicating how quickly papers are cited. This metric is published annually in the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) and relies on data from Web of Science.

3.2 Article-Level Metrics (ALMs)

Article-level metrics (ALMs) quantify the impact of published articles by measuring their discussion and sharing. ALMs use sources like citation counts, PDF downloads, and HTML views to provide quantitative indicators at the article level. The Article Impact Factor (AIF) calculates the number of citations received by individual articles. ALMs offer insights into an article's impact, including views, downloads, and citations.

1. Altmetrics provide a broader perspective on research impact by tracking online mentions, downloads, and social media shares. They consider sources like peer reviews, Wikipedia citations, research blogs, media coverage, Mendeley bookmarks, and social media mentions. Altmetrics offer immediate insights into research activity across various platforms post-publication.
2. ALMs as a valuable tool: ALMs are essential for measuring the impact of research articles. Leading publishers like PLOS, Scopus, Nature Publishing Group, and BioMed Central have integrated ALMs into their systems to offer a comprehensive view of an article's reach and engagement. ALMs encompass both academic and social metrics, providing researchers with valuable insights into how their work is perceived by the scientific community and the

general public. This data is displayed alongside individual journal articles, enabling authors to monitor the impact of their research in real-time.

3.3 Author-Level Metrics

Author-level metrics, such as the h-index and g-index, evaluate an author's impact in the scientific community. These metrics consider factors like the number of publications, citations, and collaboration networks to gauge an author's influence and productivity.

1. The h-index is a metric that evaluates a researcher's impact by counting the number of articles that have been cited at least as many times as their position in a list. It can be applied to various datasets and is available on platforms like Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Scopus. To calculate your h-index, list your publications and arrange them by citation count, identifying the point where citations match or exceed the publication's position. Databases and online tools can provide h-index values. The h-index measures an individual researcher's impact, not which of a journal, with a higher value indicating greater scholarly output.

Articles	Citations
1	33
2	30
3	20
4	15 (i10)
5	7
6	6 (h-index)
7	5
8	4

2. The g-index ranks articles based on their citations, ensuring that the top g articles collectively have at least g^2 citations. It is an enhancement of the h-index, giving more weight to highly-cited articles. Derived from sources like Google Scholar, the g-index complements the h-index by considering additional citations beyond the specific h-index threshold. A researcher with a g-index has at least twenty publications with a total of at least four hundred citations, giving more weight to highly cited articles.

By considering these metrics, researchers and institutions can better understand the impact of scholarly work and make informed decisions about where to publish and how to assess the influence of individual researchers.

4. Google Scholar

These metrics are used by researchers, institutions, and funding agencies to assess the quality and impact of research outputs and make informed decisions about research funding and collaboration. To access full-text articles from your library on Google Scholar, enable direct links in the settings menu by clicking the three lines in the top left corner of the screen.

To access Library Links, go to Settings, select Library Links, search for your library, check the box next to it, and save your changes.

Google Scholar Metrics provide authors with a tool to assess the impact and visibility of their recent articles in scholarly publications. It offers a summary of recent citations to help authors decide where to publish their new research. Users can explore the top 100 publications in various languages, ranked by their five-year h-index and h-median metrics. By clicking on a publication's h-index number, users can see which articles received the most citations and from whom. Publications can be explored by specific research areas like Engineering & Computer Science or Health & Medical Sciences, and subcategories such as Databases & Information Systems or Development Economics. While browsing by research area is limited to English publications, users can search for publications in any language using keywords in their titles. Google Scholar supports multiple languages including English, Portuguese, Spanish, German, Russian, French, Japanese, Korean, Polish, Ukrainian, and Indonesian. It's important to note that Scholar Metrics extract data based on the index as of July 2024.

Available Metrics:

- ➔ H-index: The largest number of articles in a publication that have been cited at least that many times each.
- ➔ H-core: The top cited h articles that form the basis of the h-index.
- ➔ H5-median: The median citation count in the h-core represents the distribution of citations. It is the median number of citations for the articles that contribute to the h5-index of a publication.
- ➔ H5-index: The h5 index is an author-level metric that measures the impact of a researcher's articles. To have an h5 index, an academic must have at least 20 articles, each with at least 20 citations. It was proposed by Jorge E. Hirsch in 2005.
- ➔ i10-index: The i10-index is a metric created by Google Scholar in 2011 to measure the impact of an author. It represents the number of publications by a researcher that have received at least ten citations.

Scholar Metrics analyze articles published between 2019 and 2023 based on citations in Google Scholar up to July 2024. The analysis includes indexed journal articles and selected conference papers in Engineering and Computer Science from reputable sources. Excluded are court opinions, patents, books, and dissertations, as well as publications with fewer than 100 articles or lacking citations from 2019 to 2023. Scholar Metrics provide insights into recent scholarly works, but smaller publications may not be fully represented.

If a specific journal is not listed, try searching using its abbreviated or alternate title. Google Scholar profiles allow authors to showcase their academic publications, monitor citations, observe trends, and calculate metrics. Making your profile public can enhance visibility in Google Scholar search results. Setting up and managing a profile is straight forward, even with multiple articles or shared names. You can categorize articles, update metrics automatically, and choose to review or manually update your publications.

To host your academic papers in university repositories, use Eprints, Digital Commons, or DSpace software. Ensure your website meets technical guidelines by reviewing our documentation. Google Scholar can increase global visibility. We collaborate with publishers to index academic materials such as peer-reviewed papers, theses, preprints, and technical reports on Google and Google Scholar. This section offers policy and technical guidance for scholarly publishers and societies. For webmasters' technical guidelines, visit this link. Google's mission is to make information universally accessible. We appreciate libraries and librarians for their support in achieving this goal. To enhance access to scholarly texts for your patrons through Google Scholar, connect library links to an OpenURL-compatible link resolver like SFX, 360 Link, LinkSource, or WebBridge. Contact your link resolver vendor with your library's subscriber IPs and preferred link text for registration. The vendor will update your electronic holdings and share this information with Google Scholar for indexing. Your library links should appear in Google Scholar within one to two weeks. For changes or removal of registration, contact your vendor. If switching to a different link resolver, ensure the old vendor deletes your record and the new vendor adds a new one. Vendor modifications should reflect in Google Scholar within one to two weeks. Library Search allows patrons to easily check the availability of books in their local library or request a loan. This service is particularly helpful for finding print resources like textbooks and monographs. To use Library Search, you need to be part of a union catalog like OCLC's Open WorldCat. Your bibliographic records are shared with our indexing system through the union catalog, and we provide links to access your library's catalog. Registration with us is not necessary for Library Search. If you have any inquiries about Library Search, please contact your union catalog for assistance.

Table 1: Top 10 Publications

Sl. No.	Publication	h5-index	h5-median
1.	Nature	488 (39.58%)	745 (60.42%)
2.	IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition	440 (38.97%)	689 (61.03%)
3.	The New England Journal of Medicine	434 (32.61%)	897 (67.39%)
4.	Science	409 (39.25%)	633 (60.75%)
5.	Nature Communications	375 (43.25%)	492 (56.75%)
6.	The Lancet	368 (35.18%)	678 (64.82%)
7.	Neural Information Processing Systems	337 (35.44%)	614 (64.56%)
8.	Advanced Materials	327 (43.78%)	420 (56.22%)
9.	Cell	320 (39.90%)	482 (60.10%)
10.	International Conference on Learning Representations	304 (34.23%)	584(65.77%)

Figure1: Top 10 Publications

The table and figure 1 display the top 10 publications based on their h5-index and h5-median combined results. The New England Journal of Medicine holds the top spot with a score of 13.26%, followed by Nature at 12.29%, IEEE/CVF at 11.25%, The Lancet at 10.42%, and Science at 10.38%. Neural Information Processing Systems ranks sixth with 9.48%, followed by the International Conference on Learning Representations at 8.85%, Nature Communications at 8.64%, Cell at 7.99%, and Advanced Materials at 7.44%.

Figure 2: Top 10 Funding Agencies

The figure 2 displays the top 10 funding agencies supporting the indexing of our country's journals on Google Scholar. The European Commission leads with 87%, followed by the Government of Spain at 80%. The US National Institute of Health ranks third with 74%, followed by the US Department of Energy and the US National Science Foundation at 72% and 62% respectively. The German Research Foundation is at 57%, the Department of Science and Technology in India at 56%, the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council in Canada at 52%, the National Natural Science Foundation in China at 50%, and the US Department of Defense at 48%. Funding agencies often require research articles to be publicly available.

Table 2: Different Subject & Sub Categories

Sl. No.	Subjects	Sub Categories	
1.	Business, Economics & Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Accounting & Taxation ✓ Business, Economics & Management (general) ✓ Development Economics ✓ Economic History ✓ Economic Policy ✓ Economics ✓ Educational Administration ✓ Emergency Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Entrepreneurship & Innovation ✓ Finance ✓ Game Theory and Decision Science ✓ Human Resources & Organizations ✓ International Business ✓ Marketing ✓ Strategic Management ✓ Tourism & Hospitality
2.	Chemical & Material Sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Analytical Chemistry ✓ Biochemistry ✓ Ceramic Engineering ✓ Chemical & Material Sciences (general) ✓ Chemical Kinetics & Catalysis ✓ Combustion & Propulsion ✓ Composite Materials ✓ Crystallography & Structural Chemistry ✓ Dispersion Chemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Electrochemistry ✓ Inorganic Chemistry ✓ Materials Engineering ✓ Medicinal Chemistry ✓ Nanotechnology ✓ Oil, Petroleum & Natural Gas ✓ Organic Chemistry ✓ Polymers & Plastics
3.	Engineering & Computer Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Architecture ✓ Artificial Intelligence ✓ Automation & Control Theory ✓ Aviation & Aerospace Engineering ✓ Bioinformatics & Computational Biology ✓ Biomedical Technology ✓ Biotechnology ✓ Ceramic Engineering ✓ Civil Engineering ✓ Combustion & Propulsion ✓ Computational Linguistics ✓ Computer Graphics ✓ Computer Hardware Design ✓ Computer Networks & Wireless Communication ✓ Computer Security & Cryptography ✓ Computer Vision & Pattern Recognition ✓ Computing Systems ✓ Data Mining & Analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Materials Engineering ✓ Mechanical Engineering ✓ Medical Informatics ✓ Metallurgy ✓ Microelectronics & Electronic Packaging ✓ Mining & Mineral Resources ✓ Multimedia ✓ Nanotechnology ✓ Ocean & Marine Engineering ✓ Oil, Petroleum & Natural Gas ✓ Operations Research ✓ Plasma & Fusion ✓ Power Engineering ✓ Quality & Reliability ✓ Radar, Positioning & Navigation ✓ Remote Sensing ✓ Robotics ✓ Signal Processing

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Databases & Information Systems ✓ Educational Technology ✓ Engineering & Computer Science (general) ✓ Environmental & Geological Engineering ✓ Evolutionary Computation ✓ Food Science & Technology ✓ Fuzzy Systems ✓ Game Theory and Decision Science ✓ Human Computer Interaction ✓ Library & Information Science ✓ Manufacturing & Machinery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Software Systems ✓ Structural Engineering ✓ Sustainable Energy ✓ Technology Law ✓ Textile Engineering ✓ Theoretical Computer Science ✓ Transportation ✓ Water Supply & Treatment ✓ Wood Science & Technology
4.	Health & Medical Sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Addiction ✓ AIDS & HIV ✓ Alternative & Traditional Medicine ✓ Anesthesiology ✓ Audiology, Speech & Language Pathology ✓ Bioethics ✓ Biomedical Technology ✓ Cardiology ✓ Child & Adolescent Psychology ✓ Clinical Laboratory Science ✓ Communicable Diseases ✓ Critical Care ✓ Dentistry ✓ Dermatology ✓ Developmental Disabilities ✓ Diabetes ✓ Emergency Medicine ✓ Endocrinology ✓ Epidemiology ✓ Gastroenterology & Hepatology ✓ Genetics & Genomics ✓ Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine ✓ Gynecology & Obstetrics ✓ Health & Medical Sciences (general) ✓ Heart & Thoracic Surgery ✓ Hematology ✓ Hospice & Palliative Care ✓ Immunology ✓ Medical Informatics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Nursing ✓ Nutrition Science ✓ Obesity ✓ Oncology ✓ Ophthalmology & Optometry ✓ Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery ✓ Orthopedic Medicine & Surgery ✓ Otolaryngology ✓ Pain & Pain Management ✓ Pathology ✓ Pediatric Medicine ✓ Pharmacology & Pharmacy ✓ Physical Education & Sports Medicine ✓ Physiology ✓ Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery ✓ Pregnancy & Childbirth ✓ Primary Health Care ✓ Psychiatry ✓ Psychology ✓ Public Health ✓ Pulmonology ✓ Radiology & Medical Imaging ✓ Rehabilitation Therapy ✓ Reproductive Health ✓ Rheumatology ✓ Social Psychology ✓ Surgery ✓ Toxicology ✓ Transplantation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Medicinal Chemistry ✓ Molecular Biology ✓ Natural Medicines & Medicinal Plants ✓ Neurology ✓ Neurosurgery ✓ Nuclear Medicine, Radiotherapy & Molecular Imaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Tropical Medicine & Parasitology ✓ Urology & Nephrology ✓ Vascular Medicine ✓ Veterinary Medicine ✓ Virology
5.	Humanities, Literature & Arts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ African Studies & History ✓ American Literature & Studies ✓ Asian Studies & History ✓ Canadian Studies & History ✓ Chinese Studies & History ✓ Communication ✓ Drama & Theater Arts ✓ English Language & Literature ✓ Epistemology & Scientific History ✓ Ethnic & Cultural Studies ✓ Feminism & Women's Studies ✓ Film ✓ Foreign Language Learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ French Studies ✓ Gender Studies ✓ History ✓ Humanities, Literature & Arts (general) ✓ Language & Linguistics ✓ Latin American Studies ✓ Literature & Writing ✓ Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies ✓ Music & Musicology ✓ Philosophy ✓ Religion ✓ Sex & Sexuality ✓ Visual Arts
6.	Life Sciences & Earth Sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Agronomy & Crop Science ✓ Animal Behavior & Ethology ✓ Animal Husbandry ✓ Atmospheric Sciences ✓ Biochemistry ✓ Biodiversity & Conservation Biology ✓ Bioinformatics & Computational Biology ✓ Biophysics ✓ Biotechnology ✓ Birds ✓ Botany ✓ Cell Biology ✓ Developmental Biology & Embryology ✓ Ecology ✓ Environmental & Geological Engineering ✓ Environmental Sciences ✓ Evolutionary Biology ✓ Food Science & Technology ✓ Forests & Forestry ✓ Geochemistry & Mineralogy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Geology ✓ Hydrology & Water Resources ✓ Insects & Arthropods ✓ Life Sciences & Earth Sciences (general) ✓ Marine Sciences & Fisheries ✓ Microbiology ✓ Molecular Biology ✓ Mycology ✓ Oceanography ✓ Paleontology ✓ Pest Control & Pesticides ✓ Plant Pathology ✓ Proteomics, Peptides & Aminoacids ✓ Soil Sciences ✓ Sustainable Development ✓ Sustainable Energy ✓ Virology ✓ Wood Science & Technology ✓ Zoology

7.	Physics & Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Acoustics & Sound ✓ Algebra ✓ Astronomy & Astrophysics ✓ Biophysics ✓ Computational Mathematics ✓ Condensed Matter Physics & Semiconductors ✓ Discrete Mathematics ✓ Electromagnetism ✓ Fluid Mechanics ✓ Geometry ✓ Geophysics ✓ High Energy & Nuclear Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mathematical Analysis ✓ Mathematical Optimization ✓ Mathematical Physics ✓ Nonlinear Science ✓ Optics & Photonics ✓ Physics & Mathematics (general) ✓ Plasma & Fusion ✓ Probability & Statistics with Applications ✓ Pure & Applied Mathematics ✓ Spectroscopy & Molecular Physics ✓ Thermal Sciences
8.	Social Sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Academic & Psychological Testing ✓ African Studies & History ✓ Anthropology ✓ Archaeology ✓ Architecture ✓ Asian Studies & History ✓ Bioethics ✓ Canadian Studies & History ✓ Chinese Studies & History ✓ Cognitive Science ✓ Criminology, Criminal Law & Policing ✓ Development Economics ✓ Diplomacy & International Relations ✓ Early Childhood Education ✓ Economic History ✓ Education ✓ Educational Administration ✓ Educational Psychology & Counseling ✓ Educational Technology ✓ Environmental & Occupational Medicine ✓ Environmental Law & Policy ✓ Epistemology & Scientific History ✓ Ethics ✓ European Law ✓ Family Studies ✓ Feminism & Women's Studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Forensic Science ✓ Geography & Cartography ✓ Health Policy & Medical Law ✓ Higher Education ✓ History ✓ Human Migration ✓ Human Resources & Organizations ✓ International Law ✓ Law ✓ Library & Information Science ✓ Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies ✓ Military Studies ✓ Paleontology ✓ Political Science ✓ Public Health ✓ Public Policy & Administration ✓ Science & Engineering Education ✓ Sex & Sexuality ✓ Social Sciences (general) ✓ Social Work ✓ Sociology ✓ Special Education ✓ Sustainable Development ✓ Teaching & Teacher Education ✓ Technology Law ✓ Urban Studies & Planning

Figure 3: Different Categories & Sub Categories

The table 2 and figure 3 above illustrate the wide range of subjects and subfields covered in my study. Google Scholar indexes 8 major subjects globally, with the highest number of publications in health and medical sciences (69 subcategories), followed by engineering and computer science (56), social sciences (52), life science and earth sciences (39), humanities, literature & arts (26), physics & mathematics (23), business, economics & management (16), and chemical & material sciences (17). Google Scholar is a simple and effective indexing and citation tool for researchers.

5. Conclusion

Google Scholar, launched in 2004, offers broader research coverage than Web of Science or Scopus, including web citations and references. It covers non-English publications from Africa, Asia, and Central and South America. However, it lacks a source list, clear inclusion criteria, and cited author search. Despite limitations, it is a valuable free resource for researchers. It indexes articles, abstracts, and books from major publishers and content aggregators like ProQuest, Gale, and JSTOR, including open access content. Use advanced search to narrow results by author, publication, and date. Track citations by exploring cited works from search results. Personalized researcher profiles provide insights into research impact. Publication metrics provide an overview of a journal or article's impact and usage. Journal-level metrics like the JIF indicate the average citation performance of articles in a journal. However, using journal-level metrics to evaluate individual authors is inaccurate. Author-level metrics and citations to specific articles naturally increase over time. Excessive self-citations can artificially inflate these metrics, so publication metrics should not be the sole measure of research quality or researcher merit. Google Scholar is a valuable tool for searching scholarly literature across disciplines, offering access to articles, theses, books, and more from academic publishers, professional societies, and online repositories. The platform helps researchers discover relevant work globally, ranking documents based on factors like full text, publication source, authorship, and citation frequency. Key features include searching all scholarly literature in one place, exploring related works, citations, authors, and

publications, accessing complete documents, staying updated on research, and tracking citations through a public author profile.

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